

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No6(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 344 sahifa,
16-iyun, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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CAN DUOLINGO REDUCE SPEAKING ANXIETY: A LITERATURE-BASED ANALYSIS

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Abstract: The article investigates whether Duolingo, a widely used mobile language learning application, helps language learners overcome speaking anxiety. The research synthesizes findings from pedagogical psychology, educational technology studies, and second language acquisition theory to assess whether and how Duolingo's design features can address common sources of speaking anxiety. The analysis indicates that, although Duolingo offers certain anxiety-reducing benefits through its private, low-stakes practice environment, it has significant limitations in fostering authentic communicative competence and providing real-time speaking practice.

Key words: speaking anxiety, Duolingo, mobile language learning, computer-assisted language learning, affective filter, gamification, second language acquisition.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mashhur mobil til o'rganish ilovasi bo'lgan Duolingoning til o'rganuvchilar orasida nutqiy xavotirni kamaytirish salohiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot pedagogik psixologiya, ta'lim texnologiyalari bo'yicha tadqiqotlar hamda ikkinchi tilni egallash nazariyasiga oid ilmiy qarashlarni sintez qilgan holda, Duolingo dizaynining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari nutqiy xavotirning keng tarqalgan manbalarini qay darajada bartaraf eta olishini baholaydi. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Duolingo o'zining shaxsiy va past xavfli mashq muhiti orqali xavotirni kamaytirishga ma'lum darajada yordam bersa-da, haqiqiy kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirish va real vaqt rejimidagi nutq amaliyotini shakllantirish borasida muayyan cheklolarga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: nutqiy xavotir, Duolingo, mobil til o'rganish, kompyuter yordamida til o'qitish, affektiv filtr, geymifikatsiya, ikkinchi tilni egallash.

Аннотация: Данная статья исследует потенциал Duolingo – популярного мобильного приложения для изучения языков – в снижении тревожности говорения у изучающих иностранные языки. Исследование синтезирует результаты педагогической психологии, исследований образовательных технологий и теории овладения вторым языком для оценки того, способны ли и каким образом особенности дизайна Duolingo устранять распространённые источники тревожности говорения. Анализ показывает, что, хотя Duolingo предлагает определённые возможности для снижения тревожности благодаря своей частной и низкорисковой среде практики, существуют значительные ограничения в отношении развития подлинной коммуникативной компетенции и практики говорения в реальном времени.

Ключевые слова: тревожность говорения, Duolingo, мобильное изучение языков, компьютерное обучение иностранным языкам, аффективный фильтр, геймификация, овладение вторым языком.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking anxiety represents one of the most pervasive psychological barriers in second language acquisition, affecting learners across proficiency levels and educational contexts ^[1]. The phenomenon develops through emotional states such as apprehension, worry, and fear, creating a language-learning barrier that research has shown to hinder effective language acquisition ^[2]. This anxiety manifests through various symptoms, including physiological responses such as increased heart rate and sweating, cognitive disruptions that result in mental blocks and memory lapses, and behavioral patterns that lead learners to avoid speaking opportunities. Traditional classroom environments, which often require students to perform in front of others, can intensify anxiety, particularly among learners who strive for perfection or fear negative evaluation from their peers ^[3].

The growth of mobile language-learning applications over the past decade has created new opportunities to address emotional challenges in language education. Duolingo, launched in 2011 and now serving more than 500 million users worldwide, has become one of the most widely used language-learning applications due

to its integration of gamification, adaptive algorithms, and microlearning strategies that support language development^[4]. The application's design emphasizes accessibility, learner engagement, and self-paced study, all of which educational psychology research identifies as factors that may contribute to reducing learner anxiety.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a systematic literature review methodology to investigate the extent to which Duolingo influences learners' speaking anxiety. The analytical framework draws upon three primary theoretical domains: Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis, which posits that emotional variables directly influence language acquisition by raising or lowering a metaphorical filter that facilitates or impedes language input processing^[5]; Self-Determination Theory, as applied to educational technology, which examines how digital learning environments support or undermine intrinsic motivation and psychological well-being^[6]; and research on computer-mediated communication (CMC) and its effects on language learner anxiety.

The theoretical foundation for understanding speaking anxiety in second-language contexts originates from the seminal work of Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, who established foreign language anxiety as a distinct construct separate from general anxiety^[1]. Research findings indicate that speaking anxiety negatively affects the development of oral proficiency, creating a cyclical pattern in which anxiety discourages participation in speaking activities, thereby limiting skill development and further intensifying anxiety responses^[2].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Digital language-learning platforms generate new patterns of anxiety through multiple pathways. Research on computer-assisted language learning (CALL) demonstrates that asynchronous and self-paced learning environments reduce the immediacy pressure associated with real-time communication, enabling learners to formulate responses without experiencing the time-related stress that often accompanies face-to-face interaction^[7]. Studies examining learner perceptions of CALL environments consistently report lower levels of anxiety compared to traditional classroom speaking activities. Participants frequently identify the absence of human observers and the opportunity to repeat exercises without embarrassment as key factors contributing to reduced anxiety^[8]. One of the principal advantages of gamification lies in its capacity to reduce anxiety by framing mistakes as a natural component of the learning process rather than as personal failures. Learners receive immediate automated feedback, which is often perceived as less intimidating than direct teacher evaluation. Furthermore, the platform's gradual progression through increasing levels of difficulty and its short lesson format enable learners to experience frequent successes, thereby strengthening confidence through incremental achievement.

However, gamification may also introduce additional sources of anxiety. Competitive features, such as leaderboards, can generate stress among learners who feel pressured to outperform their peers, while maintaining daily streaks may create concerns regarding consistent performance and engagement^[9]. Duolingo incorporates voice-recognition technology to evaluate speaking practice through a speech-to-text system, allowing learners to practice speaking privately. In theory, this feature may benefit learners experiencing speaking anxiety because it removes the presence of human listeners while preserving opportunities for oral language practice. Nevertheless, this approach presents several important limitations. The algorithmic evaluation system primarily assesses pronunciation accuracy at the phoneme and word levels, but it does not adequately evaluate communicative effectiveness, prosodic features, interactional competence, or the ability to use language appropriately in authentic communicative situations^[10].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis of the reviewed literature suggests a nuanced answer to the question of whether Duolingo can reduce speaking anxiety. Addressing this question requires distinguishing between different dimensions of anxiety and recognizing the limitations of the application's scope. The available evidence supports the conclusion that Duolingo and similar platforms can effectively reduce certain forms of speaking anxiety while leaving others unaddressed or, in some cases, introducing new sources of anxiety. The private and self-paced nature of the application directly addresses evaluation apprehension and social comparison anxiety. Learners who experience significant anxiety during classroom speaking activities often report feeling more comfortable practicing pronunciation through the application's voice-recognition exercises. The absence of peer observation and the non-judgmental nature of automated feedback create a psychologically safer environment for practice^[7]. This finding aligns with Self-Determination Theory, which emphasizes competence support and learner autonomy as key factors in reducing anxiety within educational settings. Duolingo's design enables learners to control the pace of their practice, repeat exercises without social consequences, and progress according to their individual readiness rather than external scheduling demands, thereby promoting psychological safety.

However, the anxiety reduction achieved through these mechanisms may be more accurately described as a reduction in practice anxiety rather than communication anxiety. Practice anxiety refers to discomfort associated with language-learning activities themselves, including fear of making mistakes, concerns about pronunciation accuracy, and apprehension regarding teacher or peer evaluation during practice. Communication anxiety, by contrast, encompasses fear and apprehension associated with authentic communicative situations that involve meaning negotiation, unpredictable interaction patterns, and real-world social consequences. Duolingo's effectiveness in reducing practice anxiety does not necessarily translate into a reduction in communication anxiety because the application offers limited opportunities for authentic, synchronous, and human-mediated interaction—the very conditions that trigger the most intense forms of speaking anxiety for many language learners. Although voice-recognition exercises provide opportunities for oral production, they lack essential features of real conversation, including unpredictability, real-time processing demands, interpersonal dynamics, and communicative urgency^[10].

Furthermore, research examining the long-term effects of relying exclusively or primarily on app-based learning suggests the possibility of anxiety displacement rather than genuine anxiety resolution. Learners who develop language proficiency through Duolingo but have limited experience interacting with other people may experience heightened anxiety when required to communicate in authentic situations. In such cases, learners may acquire substantial linguistic knowledge without developing corresponding communicative confidence^[9]. This phenomenon reflects the distinction between controlled practice in low-anxiety environments and variable practice that gradually introduces anxiety-provoking communicative challenges in manageable stages. Effective anxiety reduction in language learning requires not only safe practice environments but also systematic desensitization through progressively challenging communicative experiences. This is an area in which mobile language-learning applications face significant limitations.

The gamification elements of Duolingo introduce additional complexity into the analysis of anxiety. Although game-based learning can reduce anxiety by encouraging playfulness and normalizing errors as part of the learning process, competitive features may simultaneously generate performance-related pressure. Learners who become highly invested in maintaining streaks or achieving top positions on leaderboards often report experiencing stress and feelings of obligation associated with application use^[4]. While this form of anxiety differs from speaking anxiety, it nevertheless constitutes an affective barrier that may negatively influence the learning experience and create associations between language learning and stress.

CONCLUSION

The question of whether Duolingo can reduce speaking anxiety warrants a qualified affirmative response accompanied by several important caveats. The application demonstrates the capacity to reduce specific dimensions of speaking anxiety, particularly evaluation apprehension and practice-related stress, through its private, self-paced, and non-judgmental learning environment. For learners whose anxiety primarily stems from fear of peer judgment or teacher criticism, Duolingo provides a valuable practice space in which initial confidence and pronunciation skills can be developed without triggering these particular anxiety sources. Nevertheless, Duolingo cannot comprehensively address speaking anxiety in its broader sense because it provides limited opportunities for authentic communicative interaction. Moreover, the application may unintentionally encourage learners to avoid rather than confront the interpersonal communication challenges that lie at the heart of communication anxiety.

From a pedagogical perspective, the most effective approach is likely to involve the integrated use of applications such as Duolingo as supplementary tools for low-anxiety skill development, combined with systematic exposure to increasingly challenging communicative situations involving human interlocutors. Such an approach allows learners to build foundational confidence while simultaneously developing the communicative competence required for real-world interaction. Future research should examine the longitudinal anxiety trajectories of learners using blended approaches compared with those relying exclusively on app-based or classroom-based instruction. Further studies should also investigate the transferability of confidence gained through app-based learning to authentic communicative contexts and explore hybrid instructional models that strategically integrate technological and interpersonal practice opportunities to optimize both language development and anxiety management.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №6(5)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.